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CHALLENGES IN SCIENCE OF NOWADAYS

Proceedings of the 2nd
International Scientific and
Practical Conference

WASHINGTON, USA

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PhD students, teachers, scientists, research workers of higher educational institutions, research institutes and industrial enterprises are invited to participate in the conference. The conference provides an interdisciplinary forum for researchers, practitioners and scholars to present and discuss the most recent innovations and developments in modern science. The aim of conference is to enable academics, researchers, practitioners and college students to publish their research findings, ideas, developments, and innovations.

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MARKETING, ADVERTISING AND PR

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**TYPICAL FORECASTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNET
MARKETING IN UKRAINE**

No matter how progressive and in-demand Internet marketing may be today, still there are many issues in the field of its implementation and use in the organization. Most problems are already successfully solved in the world. However, in Ukraine the issues of overcoming them are only becoming relevant.

Having analyzed the main problems [1] that exist today and hinder the development of Internet marketing in Ukraine, we can distinguish on their basis the main tendencies, prospects and forecasts for possible changes in Internet marketing systems in the near future..

First of all, given that the Internet marketing industry is changing very fast, process automation will be the focus of attention for company executives. Anything that can be automated will be automated. The speed of implementation of automation today is literally synonymous with the speed of business growth. By keeping one's ear to the ground and monitoring the market, enterprise will implement automated systems at all levels, from chatbots already in operation today, to automated order management systems, where communication between a real employee of the company and its client will be reduced to zero. This will not mean a complete lack of contact and the ability to contact the business, but it will greatly reduce costs and save time for both parties [2-4].

The next prediction is the increasing involvement of the NPS and LTV business metrics in enterprise operations. At first glance, these are minor changes, but in fact, these techniques allow the business to understand how satisfied the customer is with the level of service or product quality, what percentage of customers themselves promote products, what level of return on investment invested in online marketing for each individual consumer [7]. Additionally, LTV The methodology allows to identify the most "important" clients for the company from the financial point of view.

NPS operates on a fairly straightforward formula (1) [6] and shows overall customer loyalty, highlighting detractors (in other words, it shows brand critics, the most persistent authors of negative reviews and future clients of competitors), neutrals (i.e., those customers, who rarely generate negative but give no assurance that they will remain customers in the future) and promoters (in other words, brand fans, long-time customers who actively promote products and generate positive reviews).

$$NPS = \frac{\sum P - \sum C}{\sum R} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

there:

$\sum P$ – the number of promoters;

$\sum C$ – the number of brand critics;

$\sum R$ – the number of respondents;

LTV works with the more sophisticated algorithm (2) [5] and helps to determine the following:

- real ROI by CAC;
- customer lifetime value against CAC;
- target audience
- customer retention strategy;
- clear customer segmentation based on their value.

$$LTV = ((T \times AOV) \times AGM) \times ALT \quad (2)$$

there:

T – average number of orders per month;

AOV – average order check value;

AGM – average profit share in revenue;

ALT – average length of customer relationship with the company (in months);

Another forecast for the development of Internet marketing in Ukraine is the transition from storing information about internal and external communications of the company from Exel (or in general in standard Notepad software) to specialized business process optimization services (for example, «Bitrix24» And «AmoCRM») because they store and carry useful information at the same level as enterprise customer analytics.

Undoubtedly, Internet marketing in Ukraine will develop rapidly in the coming years, as foreign companies with powerful web representation enter the market. There are already many multinational online stores that Ukrainians use today. To compete with them, the domestic business will pay more and more attention to the tools of Internet marketing and will study its main trends, fighting for the client and their own prosperity.

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